

TRIFFID

Autonomous Robotic Aid For increasing First responders efficiency

D5.1: Human factors analysis and participatory design toolkit

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Lead beneficiary	CNR
Authors	Francesca Fracasso (CNR), Gabriella Cortellessa (CNR), Chrysa Alexia (ITML)
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List of contributors	
Contributing Partner	Contributors
CNR	Francesca Fracasso
CNR	Gabriella Cortellessa
ITML	Chrysa Alexia
Reviewing Partner	Reviewers
PUI	Philippe Besson
FRD	Robbert Heinecke

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents the human factors analysis and participatory design toolkit developed within the TRIFFID project to support the design, development, and evaluation of human–robot teaming technologies for disaster response. It addresses the need for human-centred, reliable, and ethically sound solutions for complex, safety-critical environments involving first responders and advanced technological systems.

The document integrates evidence from the literature, empirical data, and qualitative investigations to examine how individual, contextual, and socio-technical human factors influence performance, wellbeing, decision-making, trust, workload, and situation awareness during emergency operations. At the individual level, the analysis highlights adaptive coping, cognitive flexibility, and self-efficacy as protective factors, while maladaptive strategies are associated with poorer cognitive outcomes.

At the socio-technical level, a systems perspective grounded in Distributed Situation Awareness and operationalised through the EAST framework is adopted to analyse task, information, and coordination dynamics in human–robot collaboration. Participatory design methodologies are used to systematically incorporate end-user perspectives and align technological development with real operational practices.

The deliverable concludes with a set of recommendations guiding the design, development and evaluation of the TRIFFID system, integrating frameworks from social robotics and socio-technical approach with particular attention to usability, workload management, situation awareness, trust, and ethical constraints, providing a foundation for robust and user-centred human–robot teaming solutions. By translating human factors and sociotechnical design principles into concrete design and evaluation recommendations, this deliverable supports tangible operational benefits for first responders in real-world deployments. The proposed guidelines contribute to improving operational effectiveness by reducing cognitive and physical workload, enhancing situation awareness in dynamic and uncertain environments, and fostering appropriate trust in robotic and AI-enabled systems. This, in turn, can support faster and more informed decision-making, safer coordination within distributed teams, and more reliable human–robot teaming during time-critical response operations. Furthermore, the focus on usability and ethical constraints helps mitigate risks related to technology misuse, over-reliance, or rejection, supporting sustainable adoption in operational contexts.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Explanation
HRI	Human-Robot Interaction
HCI	Human-Computer Interaction
UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicle
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
EAST	Event Analysis of Systemic Teamwork
AR	Augmented Reality
PTSD	Post-traumatic stress disorder
DSA	Distributed Situation Awareness
FR	First Responder
EADRCC	Euro-Atlantic Disaster Response Coordination Centre
USAR	Urban Search and Rescue
UPD	User Persona Development
SBD	Scenario-based design
PD	Participatory Design
HTA	Hierarchical Task Analysis
CDM	Critical Decision Method
LLM	Large Language Model

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

The purpose of this document is to present the human factors analysis and the participatory design framework developed within the TRIFFID project, in line with the objectives of Tasks T5.1 (Human Factors for efficient interaction with humans) and T5.2 (Sociotechnical integration and participatory design). The document provides a structured understanding of how individual, contextual, and socio-technical human factors influence first responders' performance, wellbeing, and interaction with robotic and digital systems during emergency management operations.

Specifically, this deliverable reports on the activities carried out within T5.1, focusing on factors affecting the design of HRI and HCI components in terms of system usability in interactions with first responders in the field, Ground-Station operators, and potential civilians. The analysis integrates insights from the literature with empirical and qualitative investigations involving first responders, coordinators, and technical experts. In line with the proposal, the deliverable addresses cognitive, emotional, and organizational factors shaping workload, stress, situation awareness, trust, and decision-making in safety-critical scenarios, both independently of technology and in interaction with robotic and AI-based systems.

In addition, the document presents the sociotechnical and participatory design framework developed within T5.2, based on social robotics approaches, participatory design methodologies, and foresight/future thinking activities. These methodologies are adopted to ensure that end-user perspectives are systematically incorporated throughout the design and development of the TRIFFID system, and that first responders do not feel obstructed or threatened by the deployment of autonomous robotic systems. The proposed framework contributes to defining principles, criteria, and processes for effective human-machine collaboration configurations.

Finally, the document provides a set of design recommendations derived from human factors analysis and participatory activities. These recommendations are intended to inform system design (T6.1), deployment guidelines, and operational protocols (T5.3), as well as the design of training curricula (T5.4) supporting the development of usable, human-centred, and ethically grounded solutions for human-robot teaming in disaster response scenarios.

1.2 Structure of the document

This document is structured as follows.

Section 1 introduces the scope and objectives of the deliverable and outlines its role within the TRIFFID project.

Section 2 provides an overview of human factors in emergency situations. It first examines individual-level factors, such as personality traits, coping strategies, self-efficacy, and decision-making styles, and their influence on stress, workload, and situation awareness. It then extends the analysis to contextual and environmental factors that shape human performance during emergency operations.

Section 3 introduces participatory design as the methodological foundation for integrating human factors into system development. This section describes the main participatory design methodologies

adopted in TRIFFID, including contextual inquiry, user persona development, scenario-based design, and cross-cutting techniques such as interviews and workshops.

Section 4 presents the analysis of human factors within the TRIFFID socio-technical system. It discusses how human and non-human agents interact within distributed emergency response teams and introduces Distributed Situation Awareness as the conceptual framework guiding the analysis. The section also describes the application of the Event Analysis of Systemic Teamwork (EAST) framework to model task, social, and information networks.

Section 5 synthesizes the findings into a set of recommendations for the design, development and evaluation of the TRIFFID system. These recommendations address system-level, HRI, HCI, and AR-related design aspects, with particular attention to usability, workload management, situation awareness, trust, and ethical constraints. The deliverable eventually provides recommendations supporting the developers in the application of human-factors driven design within TRIFFID.

Section 6 concludes the document by summarizing the main contributions and outlining how the presented human factors insights support the broader objectives of the TRIFFID project.

2 Human factors in emergency situations

2.1 Individual differences in disaster management

There are individual factors that play a role in emergency operations independently of the presence or use of technology. These include stable personal characteristics, such as personality traits, coping strategies, prior experience, and self-efficacy, which can influence how first responders perceive stress, workload, and situation awareness during critical events. Such factors may predispose individuals to different levels of vulnerability or resilience when operating in high-pressure environments, regardless of whether technological support is available.

Rescue workers are frequently exposed to prolonged emotional distress, as they face potentially traumatic events during missions and experience ongoing work-related stress. In this context, the ability to effectively regulate negative emotions appears to be crucial for managing occupational strain and preserving mental health. There is evidence that individual characteristics can somehow play a role in how people experience stressing events, with a specific emphasis on crisis management. For example, coping strategies have been identified as influencing factors. A study by Gärtner et al. (2019) identified rumination and suppression as coping strategies associated with increased work-related stress and a higher incidence of stress-related symptoms. Conversely, acceptance was linked to fewer symptoms, while, somewhat unexpectedly, avoidance was also associated with reduced work-related stress. No significant effects were observed for reappraisal or problem-solving strategies.

Moreover, given that overexposure to trauma and ineffective coping mechanisms may lead to the development of Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD), it is essential to examine the factors that influence such outcomes. A recent meta-analysis by Martinez and Blanch (2024) highlighted that rescue workers represent a high-risk group for PTSD. The prevalence of PTSD among this population appears to be significantly influenced by geographic and cultural factors, as well as by the type of assessment used. Coping strategies also play a critical role. These strategies vary among individuals and may differ across professions and types of traumatic exposure.

Despite the extensive literature on stress and coping, few studies have specifically examined how individual firefighters deal with trauma. For example, Theleritis et al. (2020) found that firefighters employing minimization and blame as coping mechanisms were more likely to develop PTSD, suggesting that the immediate coping responses following a traumatic event may influence the long-term psychological impact.

Similarly, a systematic review by Diaz Tamayo et al. (2022) found that first responders often relied on maladaptive coping strategies, particularly avoidance and emotional disconnection, to reduce perceived stress and avoid confronting difficult situations. These maladaptive strategies were strongly correlated with symptoms of PTSD, burnout, psychiatric morbidity, and chronic stress. In contrast, adaptive strategies such as acceptance, positive reinterpretation, problem-focused coping, self-efficacy, and both social and instrumental emotional support were identified as protective factors. Strengthening the use of such adaptive strategies may help emergency personnel better manage stress and prevent long-term psychological harm. Promoting active coping strategies over avoidant ones is therefore strongly recommended.

Additional evidence indicates that job experience and confrontive coping are significant predictors of psychiatric morbidity, while job experience, distancing, escape-avoidance, and positive reappraisal

significantly predict posttraumatic morbidity [Chang03]. Interestingly, rescue workers with longer job experience were found to be at greater risk for developing psychiatric and posttraumatic distress, possibly due to cumulative exposure to traumatic incidents.

Other individual differences, including personality traits, also appear to influence the coping strategies adopted by first responders. Mitchell (1983) proposed the concept of a “Rescue Personality,” later expanded by Mitchell and Bray (1990), characterized by the following traits: Calm and composed, with low levels of neuroticism; High extraversion, with sociable and novelty-seeking tendencies; Low openness, favouring tradition and predictability; High conscientiousness, marked by strong attention to detail and high performance standards; High agreeableness, with strong empathy and a desire to help others; High risk- and competition-seeking, showing a preference for action, challenge, and excitement.

Recent empirical findings offer partial support for this personality profile. For instance, Klee and Renner (2013) found that EMS personnel scored lower on neuroticism and openness but higher on conscientiousness and risk/competition seeking compared to the general population. However, they also showed lower agreeableness and no significant differences in extraversion.

Furthermore, Stępką-Tykwińska et al. (2019) found that firefighters with a higher propensity for risk-taking demonstrated greater coping flexibility, characterized by a broader and more variable repertoire of coping strategies. Their findings also suggest that length of service may moderate the relationship between empathy and coping flexibility, particularly in terms of the diversity of strategies employed.

However, it remains unexplored whether, and how, other individual factors (e.g. decision-making styles and burnout risk) may influence psychological status in specific crisis management situations. This includes not only the risk of experiencing psychological distress, but also individual perceptions of self-efficacy and situational awareness during the task, which can act both in the performance and as mediators in determining long-term psychological outcomes.

Table 1 provides an overview of relevant individual-level human factors. It links each factor (such as personality, expertise, group orientation, and self-efficacy) to its potential influence on performance and stress, identifies suitable measurement tools, and specifies when and why these factors should be assessed. This structure supports both baseline and ongoing profiling, supporting a dynamic adaptation of system interactions to individual differences.

Table 1 Human factors related to the individual characteristics

Human factor related to individuals	Influence on	Measures
Personality (Extraversion, Emotional stability and Sensation Seeking)	Performance, perceived workload, stress	TIPI [Gosling03] EPQ-R [Eysenck85] SSS-V [Zuckerman75]
Expertise	Performance, self-efficacy	Ad hoc questionnaire
Group orientation	Attitude towards teamwork (possibly affecting trust and cooperation)	Team Effectiveness Questionnaire (TEQ; Larson & LaFast, 2001)
Self-efficacy	Performance, perceived stress	Crisis self-efficacy questionnaire [Park19]
Coping styles	Performance, perceived stress	Brief COPE Inventory [Carvet97], FCSQ – [Basińska21]

Decision making styles	Performance, teamwork	MDMQ – [Mann97]
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Table 1 summarizes environment-related human factors and their impact on cognitive and team processes. For each factor, it identifies its influence on information processing, decision making, and teamwork, the methods used for assessment (self-report and psychophysiological measures), and the actors involved. The table highlights how contextual and environmental conditions shape human performance and system interaction.

Table 2 Human factors related to the situation

Human factor related to the situation	Influence on	Measures
Stress levels	Information processing Decision making	Self-report (SSSQ, Helton, 2004; PSS – [Cohen93]) Psychophysio: cardiovascular parameters, electrodermal activity, EEG, oculomotor
Workload	Information processing Decision making	Self-report (NASA-TLX, Multiple Resources Questionnaire – MRS, Boles et al., 2007) Psychophysio: cardiovascular parameters, EEG, oculomotor
Trust	Teamwork	Self-report (ad-hoc), behaviour Psychophysio: cardiovascular parameters, EEG, oculomotor
Vigilance	Performance Decision making	Related to stress and workload
Situation awareness	Performance Decision making	Event Analysis of Systemic Teamwork (EAST, [Stanton18]) SART-10 [Taylor90]

2.2 Human factors in socio-technical systems

When moving from an individual to a socio-technical perspective, the introduction of technology brings additional layers of complexity, notably through the presence of non-human agents within the system. These agents can be either active, such as autonomous or semi-autonomous robots capable of decision-making and action, or passive, such as sensors and monitoring devices that collect and transmit information without direct autonomy. The inclusion of these non-human agents fundamentally alters the dynamics of the system and the distribution of tasks and responsibilities among human operators.

A socio-technical system is a system in which social elements (e.g., people, teams, organizational structures, practices, and culture) and technical elements (e.g., tools, technologies, machines, and procedures) are interdependent and jointly shape system performance. The functioning, safety, and effectiveness of the system emerge from the interactions between its human and non-human components rather than from the behaviour of individual elements in isolation [Trist51, Baxter11].

In socio-technical systems, optimal performance is achieved by jointly optimizing social and technical subsystems, acknowledging that changes in one part of the system can have significant effects on others [Trist81]. This perspective has been widely adopted in Human Factors and safety-critical domains, where system outcomes depend on coordination, communication, and shared understanding across distributed human and technological agents [Hollnagel12, Stanton13].

Ideally, technology in emergency management should contribute to a reduction of workload, particularly cognitive workload, by supporting information processing, decision-making, and coordination. This objective is closely tied to usability: poorly designed systems may instead increase workload, create confusion, or overwhelm operators with excessive or poorly structured information. Therefore, interaction with technological systems should be intuitive, efficient, and aligned with the operational context of first responders.

In addition, technology should support appropriate levels of vigilance and alertness. On the one hand, it should prevent overload by filtering, prioritizing, and aggregating information; on the other hand, it should avoid under-stimulation, which may lead to reduced situational awareness and lowered readiness. Achieving this balance is particularly critical in emergency contexts, where both information saturation and information scarcity can have severe consequences.

The introduction of technology also has important implications for trust. Trust dynamics change when information is mediated, processed, or generated by technological systems, especially when these systems perform tasks that were traditionally under human control. First responders must trust not only the accuracy of the information provided but also the reliability and predictability of the technology itself. This trust is strongly influenced by how information is represented and communicated: clarity, transparency, and lack of ambiguity are essential to ensure correct interpretation and effective use of technological outputs.

Finally, the integration of technology into emergency operations should be as non-disruptive as possible. A seamless integration that respects existing workflows, practices, and organizational cultures is crucial to avoid resistance and misuse. Radical changes to established procedures may increase cognitive burden and reduce acceptance, particularly in time-critical situations. This aspect is closely related to familiarity with technology, which may vary significantly among first responders and may also be influenced by individual characteristics, including personality traits and prior technological experience.

Overall, a human-centred approach to the design and deployment of emergency management technologies is essential to ensure that technological innovation genuinely enhances performance, safety, and resilience, rather than introducing new sources of risk within already complex and demanding operational environments.

In the specific case of TRIFFID, a socio-technical-oriented approach should be taken. Indeed, when introducing technological systems, it is essential to ensure that they represent added value compared to usual practices, not only in terms of achieving the intended objectives, but also with respect to the quality of first responders' experience.

In this sense, the design and development of technological solutions should be guided by ergonomic principles of usability and acceptance, usually considered in the fields of HRI and HCI, with the goal of promoting adaptive levels of stress, workload, and situational awareness.

In this sense, human factors that concur in the context of emergency management can be related to individual characteristics and to the specific context as well.

With these perspectives in mind, the human factors described in the previous section that can play a role in the context of disaster management, should here be considered the interaction with the technology as well.

In the context of TRIFFID, many of the aspects mentioned above can be considered under a comprehensive framework that intends the involved agents as players in a socio-technical system. In fact, TRIFFID conceived a socio-technical system where human agents (first responders) closely interact with artificial agents (UGV, UAV, sensors, intelligent systems).

By assuming that in distributed teamwork, cognitive processes occur at a system, rather than individual level, the model of Distributed Situational Awareness (DSA) can be ascribed as a framework within to investigate how human factors can be considered in the design, development and assessment of the TRIFFID system.

Distributed Situation Awareness (DSA) is defined as “activated knowledge for a specific task within a system, relating to the state of the environment and how it changes over time” [Stanton06A]. Unlike individual-centred models, DSA is conceptualized at the system level rather than as knowledge contained solely within an individual’s mind. It highlights the importance of alignment and compatibility of situation awareness across multiple agents, both human and non-human, operating within the same context. This shared and compatible awareness acts as the “glue” that enables effective coordination within a distributed system.

For instance, during a large-scale bushfire, firefighters from different stations must coordinate closely with police (to receive updates on road closures), local authorities (to identify emergency shelter locations), paramedics (to manage first aid for victims), and non-human information sources such as sensors (to monitor evolving risks). When situation awareness is compatible across these agents, evacuation efforts are more likely to proceed efficiently and safely.

DSA is therefore more than the aggregate of individual situation awareness states. Instead, the underlying knowledge is distributed across the system, emerging through interactions among agents. In this perspective, situation awareness is not owned by any single actor but arises dynamically from collaborative processes within the system.

Two key factors underpin this model. First, the knowledge that supports Distributed Situation Awareness (DSA) is spread across the entire system rather than residing in a single agent. Second, information is often conveyed through implicit communication mechanisms, rather than through explicit and detailed exchanges of mental models.

Building on these core principles of situation awareness as a distributed property of a system, Stanton et al. (2004) proposed a set of tenets that may serve as the foundation for a theoretical framework. These propositions can be summarized as follows:

DSA as an emergent system property. DSA arises from the functioning of sociotechnical systems and cannot be reduced to the cognition of individual agents. Consequently, SA should be examined through the interactions among agents, with the system as a whole serving as the primary unit of analysis rather than individual humans or artefacts.

Distribution of SA across agents. Situation awareness is shared among both human and non-human agents operating within the system, with each agent holding a distinct perspective on the same situation. This perspective is shaped by prior experience, memory, training, and viewpoint, drawing on schema theory and the perceptual cycle model ([Neisser76, Salmon18]).

Dynamic information networks. Sociotechnical systems are characterised by a dynamic network of information to which each agent contributes and from which each derives a unique understanding, akin to a “hive mind” [Seeley12]. The degree of compatibility between agents’ situation awareness is

essential for safe and effective performance, while mismatches or gaps pose risks to performance, safety, and system resilience.

Transactions in awareness. DSA is sustained through continuous exchanges of awareness between agents. These transactions may occur between humans, between humans and technological artefacts, or between artefacts themselves, and can strengthen, extend, or weaken the overall DSA network. For example, humans communicate through verbal and non-verbal cues, technologies convey information via displays, alarms, or symbols, and artefacts exchange data through communication protocols.

Importance of compatible SA. Compatible situation awareness represents a critical subset of DSA. Although agents maintain different views of the situation, these perspectives must be mutually compatible to support effective system functioning. When incompatibilities arise, DSA becomes fragmented, leading to missing or misaligned awareness that undermines safe and efficient performance.

Role of genotype and phenotype schemata. Genotype and phenotype schemata play a central role in shaping both awareness transactions and compatibility. Genotype schemata are experience-based mental structures developed over time, while phenotype schemata are task-specific schemas activated during performance that guide perception and action [Stanton09]. For instance, drivers possess genotype schemata for intersections, which activate phenotype schemata that steer attention and behaviour when navigating through them.

DSA as a binding mechanism in loosely coupled systems. Distributed situation awareness acts as the cohesive force that enables loosely coupled systems to operate effectively. When DSA deteriorates, system performance declines and failures may occur. Changes in system coupling-towards tighter or looser integration-can also produce corresponding changes in DSA.

Compensation for degraded SA. Agents within a system often operate with partially degraded situation awareness. When an individual agent’s SA deteriorates to a level that threatens performance, other agents may intervene to compensate, thereby preserving DSA and preventing task or system failure.

This set of propositions highlights how situation awareness emerges from interactions among agents and how system-level performance depends on the effective distribution and coordination of awareness.

Figure 1 Distributed situation awareness in TRIFFID

Figure 1 illustrates the conceptual framework adopted to model Distributed Situation Awareness (DSA) within the TRIFFID system. The framework represents DSA as an emergent property arising from the interactions between multiple agents—both human and non-human—operating within a shared operational context.

At the core of the system, situation awareness is distributed across four main types of agents: First Responders, Ground Station Operator(s), Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV), and Unmanned Ground Vehicle (UGV). These agents continuously exchange information through bidirectional SA transactions, which support coordination, decision-making, and adaptive behaviour during emergency operations. Rather than residing within a single individual, awareness is dynamically constructed through these interactions.

The framework highlights the influence of multiple layers of factors on DSA. Individual factors, such as experience and training, goals and roles, personality traits, self-efficacy, decision-making style, group orientation, and trust, shape how human agents perceive, interpret, and act upon information. Task factors, including workload, stress, and vigilance, dynamically modulate cognitive resources and directly affect agents' ability to maintain adequate situation awareness under operational pressure.

In parallel, system factors, such as procedures, system design, and system goals, constrain and enable information flow between agents, influencing how awareness is supported or hindered by technological artefacts. At the team level, team attributes (e.g., shared mental models, cohesion, attitudes) and team processes (e.g., communication and collaboration) play a critical role in ensuring compatibility between agents' situation awareness, which is essential for effective system performance.

Overall, the model conceptualizes DSA as a system-level phenomenon that emerges from the alignment and compatibility of awareness across agents, rather than as a purely individual cognitive construct. This perspective supports the analysis of human-agent teaming in emergency contexts and provides a structured lens for evaluating how individual, task, system, and team factors jointly shape performance, safety, and resilience. Indeed, as it will be better explained in the next section, the chosen evaluation framework comes from this conceptualization.

3 Participatory design

To ensure the inclusion of human factors within the design and development process of the TRIFFID system, a participatory design approach should be given. This means that the human agent must be involved throughout the whole process with the scope to integrate their perspective and feedback.

The following sections illustrate some of the methodologies that can be considered in general for gathering feedback, as well some specific to foster the effective integration of technology.

3.1 Methodologies and techniques

Participatory design is a well-established and user-centred approach to system designing that involves end users actively in the process. In the context of the TRIFFID system, which aims at designing a robotic system for emergency response, there is a strong need to balance robotic autonomy and human control so that the system effectively supports the first responders (FRs) using it, without them feeling obstructed or restricted by the system. As disaster response is a very critical field where FRs are required to operate in life-or-death situations, incorporating the perspectives of FRs into the design process is crucial. Their active participation enables the development of a system that aligns with real operational requirements, provides a user interface based on established workflows and terminology, and increases system trust and acceptance, ultimately supporting effective and reliable human–robot collaboration in emergency scenarios.

The main participatory design methodologies considered in this context include Contextual Inquiry, User Persona Development and Scenario-Based Design, complemented by a set of Cross-Cutting Techniques with a horizontal character that serve also as means of implementation and application of the above methods.

3.1.1 Contextual inquiry

Contextual Inquiry (CI) is an ethnographic field study that combines on-site observation of end users with interactive interviews to understand users' workflows, decision-making practices, and their interactions with complex systems. By observing users while they perform real tasks in their natural operational context, contextual inquiry enables the identification of behavioural patterns and practices that are often overlooked in retrospective interviews or laboratory-based studies. Core elements of the methodology include observation in context, strong collaboration between the researcher and the user, iterative interpretation of observed actions, and a clear focus on the methods being used by the users to complete their tasks and the objectives these activities aim to achieve.

This approach is particularly well suited for safety-critical domains such as disaster response, where system use takes place under time pressure, environmental constraints, and high cognitive demands. Contextual inquiry's outputs can range from detailed task and decision-making workflows to representations of users' mental models, which subsequently serve as input for the system requirements, interface design and interaction strategies for human-robot collaboration.

Application examples of contextual inquiry principles include the participation of TRIFFID partners in large-scale emergency response exercises, such as the 20th NATO EADRCC Emergency Management Exercise "BULGARIA 2025" and the PUI USAR exercise in Moncada, as described in Section 4. These activities provided opportunities to observe operational practices and interaction patterns in realistic settings.

However, within the context of the TRIFFID project, constraints inherent to disaster response, such as the limited availability of first responders, the unpredictability of emergency situations and safety considerations, constitute the full application of contextual inquiry impractical, especially during early design phases. Additional elements of contextual inquiry are expected to be selectively incorporated at later stages, such as controlled pilot trials, where on-site feedback can be collected under time-bound and safe conditions.

3.1.2 User persona development

User Persona Development (UPD) is a widely adopted participatory design technique, using fictional persons to represent key user groups based on empirical data. It constitutes a complementary participatory design approach that helps bridge limitations arising when large-scale user involvement is not feasible. While participatory design is most effective in contexts with direct interaction between developers and relatively homogeneous user groups, it becomes more challenging in cases involving heterogeneous stakeholders, distributed teams and operational constraints, as is often the case in emergency response systems such as TRIFFID. Personas address these challenges by providing representative and structured user profiles that consolidate key goals, recurring behaviours and constraints across target user groups.

From a methodological perspective, user persona development focuses on integrating empirical user insights into representative profiles. It can be applied across multiple stages of the design process, supporting early identification of users' main characteristics, and later serving as a reference point for evaluating design concepts.

As fictional composites grounded in empirical data, personas help designers move beyond individual-specific traits, while retaining recurring patterns that are meaningful for system design and decision-making. At the same time, they provide a practical mechanism for bringing together qualitative insights and quantitative evidence, contributing to a more comprehensive representation of user requirements. By serving as an effective mechanism for communicating user understanding across multidisciplinary teams, personas promote shared mental models, support system trust and acceptance, and contribute to the development of usable and operationally relevant solutions for emergency response scenarios.

In the context of complex sociotechnical systems such as disaster response platforms, personas can be considered a conceptual mechanism for representing diverse operational perspectives and stakeholder roles within a shared design framework. By offering a common reference point for discussing user needs and system interactions, personas support alignment, without requiring constant direct access to end users.

Figure 2 illustrates a high-level example of how *persona* development can be approached in the context of disaster response systems such as TRIFFID. The example highlights the identification of key stakeholder groups involved in emergency response and their categorisation according to roles, responsibilities, and expertise, supporting the integration of diverse perspectives into representative personas.

TRIFFID Example (High-level)

1. Identify stakeholders involved in disaster response:

2. Categorize stakeholders by their roles and expertise:

3. Create personas based on gathered insights

4. Highlight persona goals, challenges and preferences

Figure 2 High-level illustration of a persona development approach for disaster response systems

3.1.3 Scenario-based design

Scenario-based design (SBD) is a narrative-driven user-centred methodology that is frequently employed in combination with user personas to support participatory design processes. While personas provide structured representations of user roles, scenarios place these representations within dynamic narratives that describe how users interact with a system while addressing real-world challenges.

In the context of the TRIFFID project, scenarios may describe for example a coordinated search and rescue operation in a partially collapsed building, where different actors (first responders, UGV operators, and command staff) interact with robotic assets and information systems in specific phases of the incident. By walking through the scenario step-by-step, stakeholders can discuss how information is received and shared, which decisions need to be supported by the system, and how responsibilities are shared as the situation evolves. These narratives allow abstract user needs to be translated into concrete requirements, taking into consideration realistic operational flows.

In TRIFFID, scenario-based discussions were utilized during the use-case requirements elicitation process that was reported in the deliverable D2.1 “*End-user requirements 1*”. In particular, narrative walkthroughs of the use cases were used to support prioritisation and validation of user needs across different operational roles.

Figure 3 presents a high-level illustrative example of how scenario-based design could be operationalised in the context of disaster response systems such as TRIFFID. The example outlines a generic workflow in which emergency response scenarios are enhanced with branched decision-making and progressively refined into role-specific narratives that could also be tailored into specific personas. Combining this method with iterative feedback, it is feasible to explore alternative decision options and identify areas for improving, supporting the refinement and prioritisation of user requirements, while remaining adaptable to different operational roles and contexts.

Figure 3 High-level illustration of an example scenario-based design workflow in the context of TRIFFID

3.1.4 Cross-cutting participatory design techniques

In addition to the participatory design methodologies described in the previous sections, there are several techniques that function as cross-cutting instruments across different PD approaches, such as focus groups, co-design workshops, interviews and journey mapping. These techniques are not always explicitly labelled as participatory design methods, as they are widely used in everyday research and design practices. Due to their horizontal nature, these techniques can be considered as means of implementation that support and complement multiple PD methodologies, rather than standalone PD approaches.

Focus groups constitute a common methodology, bringing together stakeholders of diverse expertise and operational perspectives. By facilitating structured or semi-structured group discussions, focus groups enable participants to share experiences, discuss challenges and reflect collectively on system needs. The interaction among participants often leads to richer insights than individual methods alone, as viewpoints are compared and refined through group dynamics.

Co-design workshops represent a more action-oriented and co-creative form of participatory engagement, building upon the exploratory discussions enabled by focus groups. Through structured activities and collaborative artefacts, workshops allow stakeholders to analyse challenges, shape requirements and set priorities. In contrast to open discussion formats, workshops support the systematic transformation of individual insights into shared outcomes, which makes them particularly effective in complex, multi-stakeholder contexts. Within TRIFFID, dedicated workshop sessions in physical General Assembly Meetings relied on interactive activities to collaboratively explore operational scenarios and system needs. The activities were complemented by techniques such as

MoSCoW prioritization exercises, requirement clustering, and use case validation and were further supported by digital collaboration tools, such as Miro boards, as well as by hands-on, physical facilitation materials (see D2.1 “*End-user requirements 1*”).

Interviews represent another foundational technique that complements participatory design activities across different stages of the design process. They can be employed to inform *persona* development, support scenario refinement, or collect feedback following operational activities or pilot trials. Interviews may take place in controlled settings or, where feasible, on site, allowing designers to capture detailed, context-specific insights while maintaining flexibility to explore unanticipated topics that emerge during discussion.

Journey mapping is another technique that supports participatory design by visualising user activities, decision points, and interactions over time. By collaboratively mapping user journeys, stakeholders can identify critical moments, information needs, pain points, and opportunities for system support and intervention across different phases of an operation. In the context of complex sociotechnical systems, journey mapping helps align technical design choices with real operational flows and facilitates a shared understanding of how different roles interact with the system. When extended beyond current-state representations, journey mapping can also support future-oriented thinking by enabling stakeholders to reflect on anticipated changes in workflows, decision-making, and system support across evolving operational scenarios.

3.2 Event analysis of systemic teamwork framework

Event Analysis of Systemic Teamwork (EAST) is a systems-based human factors methodology used to analyse teamwork and coordination in complex sociotechnical systems. EAST conceptualises teamwork as an emergent property of interactions between people, tasks, technologies, and the environment, rather than as the sum of individual behaviours. The method focuses on how information is distributed, transformed, and shared across a system during task execution.

Originally developed by Stanton and colleagues, EAST is grounded in Distributed Situation Awareness (DSA) theory and is particularly suited for analysing safety-critical domains such as aviation, healthcare, emergency response, and human–robot teams.

EAST is based on three key assumptions:

Teamwork is systemic

Team performance emerges from the interaction between multiple agents (human and non-human), rather than from isolated individual actions.

Situation awareness is distributed

Knowledge relevant to task performance is distributed across the system and maintained through interactions (e.g., communication, displays, procedures).

Structure matters

Task constraints, information flows, and social relationships strongly shape how teamwork unfolds.

EAST represents a system through three interconnected network models, each capturing a different aspect of teamwork:

Task network

- Describes what needs to be done

- Nodes represent tasks or events
- Links represent temporal or logical dependencies between tasks
- Useful for understanding task complexity, sequencing, and coordination requirements

Social network

- Describes who interacts with whom
- Nodes represent agents (individuals, teams, or autonomous systems)
- Links represent communication, coordination, or authority relationships
- Can be weighted or directional to capture frequency or direction of interaction

Information network

- Describes what information is required and exchanged
- Nodes represent information elements (e.g., location data, sensor outputs, commands)
- Links represent information flow between agents and artefacts
- Supports analysis of information bottlenecks, redundancy, and compatibility of situation awareness

These three networks are analysed in combination, providing a holistic view of how tasks, agents, and information interact within the system.

4 Analysis of human factors

The data collection plan for the activities described in this deliverable envisages two levels of analysis of human factors in emergency situations:

- A first level of analysis aimed at investigating individual aspects that may influence perceived levels of stress, workload, situation awareness, and self-efficacy during emergency management operations. The objective of this phase is to identify those individual characteristics that, regardless of the use of technology, may potentially expose first responders to a higher risk of experiencing distress during operations. In terms of impact, the results may primarily provide insights into the development of personalized training pathways aimed at optimizing performance and, above all, enhancing the psychological resilience of first responders in emergency situations characterized by high levels of stress.
- At a second level, the analysis focuses on human factors at the socio-technical system level. In this case, the use of technology to support emergency management operations is explicitly considered, with the aim of understanding how such technology can be leveraged to promote adaptive levels of stress, workload, and situation awareness.

In the following sections, the methodology adopted for both levels of analysis and the data collection procedures are described.

4.1 Human factors in disaster management

This investigation aims to enrich the investigation on how individual differences, specifically personality traits, self-efficacy, coping mechanisms, burnout risk, and decision-making styles, influence the perception of stress, workload, self-efficacy and situation awareness among first responders following emergency operations.

To achieve this objective, a questionnaire-based study is proposed. The findings from this study could offer valuable insights into how personal characteristics influence the psychological response to high pressure situations, contributing to a better understanding of the mental health challenges faced by first responders. Moreover, the results may inform the development of tailored training programs designed to enhance individual resilience, optimize performance under stress, and mitigate burnout risks. By aligning training interventions with the specific needs and profiles of first responders, this research could support more effective preparation strategies for emergency professionals, ultimately improving both individual wellbeing and operational effectiveness.

4.1.1 Instruments

Ten-Item Personality Inventory (TIPI – [Gosling03]). This is an extremely brief measure of the Big-Five personality dimensions offered for situations when very short measures are needed, personality is not the primary topic of interest, or researchers can tolerate the somewhat diminished psychometric properties associated with very brief measures. Personality traits Extraversion, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Emotional Stability, and Openness to Experience are investigated through 10 items to which responders have to provide an agreement rating on a 7-points Likert scale.

Brief COPE Inventory (Carvet et al., 1997). This instrument was developed to assess a broad range of coping responses, several of which had an explicit basis in theory. In this study, the "dispositional" or trait-like version is used, in which respondents report the extent to which they usually do the things

listed, when they are stressed. This instrument, through 28 items, focuses on the following dimensions: Self-distraction, Active coping, Denial, Substance use, Use of emotional support, Use of instrumental support, Behavioral disengagement, Venting, Positive reframing, Planning, Humor, Acceptance, Religion, Self-blame. Respondents are asked to answer on a 4-points Likert scale where 1 = I haven't been doing this at all, and 4 = I've been doing this a lot.

Flexibility in Coping with Stress Questionnaire (FCSQ – [Basińska21]). This 14-items questionnaire examines three subscales of flexibility, namely, Repertoire of coping strategies, Changeability, and Reflexivity. It is applied to the study of persons exposed to severe or chronic stress at work, when we want to assess the individual's ability to change their functioning in a stressful situation. Responders are asked to assess the frequency of experiencing for each item on a 4-point Likert scale.

Melbourne Decision Making Questionnaire (MDMQ – [Mann97]). This instrument (22 items) aims at investigating coping patterns identified in the conflict theory of decision making, namely basic patterns of coping with the stress generated by a difficult, potentially threatening decision. The questionnaire focuses on 4 identifiable factors (vigilance, hypervigilance, buck-passing, and procrastination). The respondent responds to the items by checking “True for me” (score 2), “Sometimes true” (score 1), or “Not true for me” (score 0).

Perceived Stress Scale (PSS – [Cohen93]). The Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) is a widely used psychological instrument developed by Sheldon Cohen to assess the degree to which individuals perceive situations in their lives as stressful. The PSS measures perceived stress, rather than actual stressful events. It is commonly used in research and clinical settings to evaluate stress levels and monitor changes due to interventions. Respondents rate each item (10-item version) on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = never to 5 = very often).

NASA-TLX [Hart88]. NASA-TLX originally consisted of two parts: the total workload is divided into six subjective subscales that are represented on a single page, serving as one part of the questionnaire: Mental Demand, Physical Demand, Temporal Demand, Performance, Effort, Frustration. Responders are asked to rate each of them on six 7-point scales. The second part of TLX intends to create an individual weighting of these subscales by letting the subjects compare them pairwise based on their perceived importance. Within the purpose of this study, just the first part will be used.

Crisis Self-Efficacy Scale (CSES – [Park19]). The CSES explore the responders self-efficacy in handling a crisis situation by asking them to report their agreement degree with respect to 12 items on a 7-point scale (“1 = Strongly Disagree” to “7 = Strongly Agree”).

Situation Awareness Rating Technique (SART-10 [Taylor90]) uses the following ten dimensions to measure operator SA: Familiarity of the situation, focussing of attention, information quantity, information quality, instability of the situation, concentration of attention, complexity of the situation, variability of the situation, arousal, and spare mental capacity. SART is administered post-trial and involves the participant rating each dimension on a seven point rating scale (1 = Low, 7 = High) in order to gain a subjective measure of SA.

4.1.2 Procedure

Participants were recruited at first during the 20th NATO EADRCC Emergency Management Exercise “BULGARIA 2025”, which was held in Montana, Bulgaria, from September 8th to September 12th, 2025. In order to enrich the sample size, the survey was then distributed across the TRIFFID partners' contacts.

First responders are asked to complete a two series of validated instruments:

- Questionnaires investigating general individual aspects assessing their personality (TIPI, 10-item), coping strategies (Brief COPE Inventory, 28-item; FCSQ, 14-item), and decision-making styles (MDMQ, 22-item) and self-efficacy in crisis scenarios (CSES, 12-item).
- Questionnaires investigating aspects related to the specific situation like levels of stress (PSS, 10-item), workload (NASA-TXL, 6-items) and situation awareness (SART, 10-item) experienced during the exercises.

Additional general information is collected about age, professional roles, field of expertise and years of experience.

Out of 50 first responders who answered the survey, data from 41 were used for the analysis. Those excluded from the analysis were mostly because of missing data.

In detail, the distribution of the participants with respect to their age, years and area of expertise, and role is described in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Sociodemographic data of participants

4.1.3 Results

In this section, some descriptive results are reported with respect to the descriptive characteristics of the first respondents involved. At first individual aspects are illustrated, followed by specific aspects related to operational experiences.

Individual characteristics possibly influencing the experiences during the operations. As it can be inferred from Figure 5 participants reveal a distinct psychological profile across several assessed dimensions. Overall, participants exhibited high levels of conscientiousness, emotional stability, and openness to experience. These traits suggest a tendency toward structured, reliable behaviours, emotional regulation under pressure, and a willingness to adapt to novel situations.

With respect to coping strategies, the results indicated a clear preference for adaptive coping mechanisms. Participants reported frequent use of active coping, planning, and positive reframing, alongside acceptance strategies. In addition, both emotional and instrumental support seeking emerged as commonly adopted approaches, highlighting a tendency to rely on social resources when managing stressful or demanding situations.

Regarding coping flexibility, participants showed high scores on the repertoire subscale, indicating a broad range of coping strategies available to them. High values were also observed for the changeability subscale, suggesting an ability to adjust coping strategies according to situational demands rather than relying rigidly on a single approach.

Decision-making style analysis revealed higher scores for buck-passing compared to procrastination and hypervigilance. This pattern suggests a greater tendency to delegate or share responsibility for decisions rather than delaying decisions or engaging in excessive and anxious information searching under pressure.

Figure 5 Individual characteristics of the participants

Finally, participants demonstrated a good level of perceived self-efficacy in crisis situations. This indicates confidence in their ability to manage challenging and high-stakes scenarios effectively, even under conditions of uncertainty and time pressure.

The graph displayed in Figure 6 shows the significant correlations emerged between individual differences and operation-related experiences in terms of Situation Awareness, workload, and perceived stress.

The findings highlight the role of individual differences in shaping how demanding situations are perceived, understood, and managed, rather than directly influencing perceived stress levels. Overall, the pattern of correlations suggests that personality traits, coping strategies, cognitive flexibility, decision-making styles, and self-efficacy primarily affect higher-order cognitive and situational processes, such as Situation Awareness, Understanding, and perceived Supply of attentional resources.

Regarding personality traits, Extraversion, Conscientiousness, and Openness to Experience were consistently associated with higher levels of Situation Awareness, Supply, and Understanding. These traits are commonly linked to proactive engagement, cognitive organization, and openness to contextual information, which may facilitate a more accurate and integrated representation of the operational environment. Notably, personality traits showed limited direct associations with perceived Stress,

suggesting that their influence may operate indirectly by shaping how situations are cognitively processed rather than by directly buffering emotional strain.

Figure 6 Significant correlations between individual characteristics and operation-related psychological aspects. The red arrows represent negative associations; blue arrows represent positive associations

Coping strategies emerged as a particularly salient set of variables. Adaptive coping strategies, such as Active Coping and Acceptance, demonstrated strong positive associations with perceived Supply, as well as with Understanding and Situation Awareness. Similarly, seeking Emotional and Instrumental Support was related to better situational comprehension and perceived availability of resources. These findings suggest that active, problem-focused, and support-oriented coping may enhance individuals' sense of control and clarity in complex situations, thereby improving cognitive and operational functioning.

In contrast, maladaptive coping strategies displayed a consistent negative pattern. Substance Use was associated with lower Demand and Supply, while Buck Passing, Procrastination, and Hypervigilance were negatively related to Supply and Understanding. Among these, Procrastination showed the strongest negative association with Understanding, indicating that avoidance and delay may substantially impair the ability to construct an accurate mental model of the situation. Together, these results underline the detrimental impact of avoidant or dysfunctional coping on cognitive clarity and perceived resource availability.

Cognitive flexibility also played a meaningful role. Higher levels of Repertoire and Changeability were associated with better Understanding, and Changeability was additionally related to higher Supply. This pattern supports the idea that flexible cognitive strategies enable individuals to adapt their interpretations and responses to situational demands, promoting a more effective integration of available information and resources.

With respect to decision-making styles, Reflexivity showed positive associations with both perceived workload (NASA-TLX) and Stress. While reflexive decision-making is often considered adaptive, this finding suggests that excessive deliberation may increase cognitive load and emotional strain, potentially reflecting over-analysis in high-demand contexts.

Finally, self-efficacy emerged as a robust positive correlate of Situation Awareness, Supply, and Understanding across all its dimensions. Individuals with higher perceived self-efficacy appear more confident in their ability to manage tasks and uncertainty, which may translate into more effective cognitive processing and situational assessment. As with personality traits, self-efficacy showed little direct association with Stress, reinforcing the notion that its primary impact lies in enhancing cognitive and situational functioning rather than directly reducing stress perceptions.

In sum, the results suggest that individual differences predominantly influence how situations are cognitively represented and managed, rather than stress levels per se. Adaptive coping, cognitive flexibility, and self-efficacy appear to function as protective factors that support effective situational processing, whereas maladaptive coping strategies and potentially excessive reflexivity are linked to poorer cognitive outcomes. These findings underscore the importance of targeting cognitive and coping processes in interventions aimed at improving performance and resilience in demanding environments.

4.2 Human factors in sociotechnical systems

4.2.1 Methodology

The methodological framework adopted to investigate human factors to consider in the design and development of the TRIFFID system integrates Hierarchical Task Analysis (HTA) and the Critical Decision Method (CDM) to inform an Event Analysis of Systemic Teamwork (EAST), enabling a comprehensive analysis at the level of the sociotechnical system (see Figure 7).

Hierarchical Task Analysis (HTA) is a human factors method used to analyse complex tasks by decomposing them into a hierarchical structure of goals, sub-goals, operations, and plans. The method starts from an overall task goal and progressively breaks it down into smaller components, making explicit the logical and temporal relationships between task elements. HTA is widely used to support system design, usability evaluation, workload assessment, and training by providing a structured representation of how tasks are performed in practice [Annett67, Duncan67, Stanton06B].

The **Critical Decision Method (CDM)** is a qualitative interview technique used to elicit expert decision-making processes in complex, time-pressured, and uncertain real-world situations. It is based on the retrospective analysis of critical incidents and employs structured probing to identify key decision points, situational cues, goals, and cognitive strategies adopted by practitioners [Klein89]. Grounded in the Naturalistic Decision-Making framework, CDM is particularly suited to studying how first responders make decisions in emergency management contexts [Klein98].

Figure 7 Methodological framework adopted to investigate human factors-related needs

HTA was employed to model the structural and procedural aspects of work, by decomposing operational goals into tasks, sub-tasks, and plans. This analysis provided a detailed representation of how activities are organised, sequenced, and distributed across human and technological agents during emergency management operations.

In parallel, CDM was used to elicit the cognitive and decision-making processes underpinning task execution. Through retrospective interviews focused on critical incidents, CDM enabled the identification of key decision points, situational cues, goals, and strategies adopted by first responders under time pressure and uncertainty. This method contributed insight into how practitioners perceive, interpret, and act upon information in dynamic emergency contexts.

The outputs of HTA and CDM were subsequently integrated within the EAST framework. EAST leverages these inputs to construct interconnected task, social, and information networks, capturing interactions between human and non-human agents and supporting the analysis of Distributed Situation Awareness (DSA) at the system level. By combining task structure and cognitive decision data, EAST allows the examination of how information is distributed, shared, and coordinated across the sociotechnical system, and how these interactions influence system performance.

Overall, this integrated approach supports a multi-level understanding of emergency operations, linking individual tasks and decisions to emergent properties of teamwork and system-level situation awareness.

4.2.2 Procedure

- Analysis of operative protocols from different sources, including the INSARAG guidelines
- EAST methodology applied by involving:

- 2 interviewees recruited via CMINE portal
- 5 first responders engaged in a workshop
- 2 interviewees engaged during the NATO exercise
- 2 coordinators experts in using the INSARAG Coordination and Management System (ICMS)
- 5 experts (including 3 developers) on the Next-Generation Incident Command Systems (NICS)
- Other feedback from 7 first responders with different expertise and roles (coordinators, divers, victim rescuer, firefighters, psychologist with expertise in supporting FR)
- Participation at a training webinar focused on the INSARAG Coordination and Management System (ICMS)
- Direct observation of field exercise (PUI USAR exercise in Moncada held in June 2025; NATO Exercise “Bulgaria 2025”. Figure 8). This activity aimed at gathering information on observable inputs and outputs of human information processing, while actions are occurring and to perform contextual inquiries.

In total, 23 Subject-Matter Experts (SMEs) participated in this phase of qualitative data gathering.

Figure 8 Some pictures from the activities of direct observation

4.2.3 Results

Specialised to the event type

There are different search and rescue departments: land and mountain rescue (often called alpine search and rescue), water search and rescue (including sea, rivers, and lakes), and urban search and rescue, which includes natural disasters such as fires, earthquakes, and floods. All these departments have their own specialized areas, and procedures differ depending on the type of event. For example, in the case of fires, fast intervention is needed to evacuate people immediately during the event, whereas for earthquakes, intervention usually takes place after the event. Some rescue procedures are more specialized than others. For instance, for earthquakes in Greece there is a national protocol followed by all teams, while for fires there is no specific standardized protocol.

Wide-area assessment

Phase 1: Define the area of the incident. This includes identifying whether there are schools or hospitals nearby, whether it is a weekday or weekend, how many victims are involved, and which areas contain the highest concentration of victims.

Phase 2: Once the most critical areas are identified, a more detailed analysis of specific areas, rooms, and individual victims is carried out.

This protocol is used for earthquakes: first, a wide-area assessment is performed, then responders move into specific areas. Victims at serious risk are assisted first, followed by less critical cases. The victim protocol begins with identifying the number of victims and then prioritizing the most serious cases.

For fires, the protocol is different and faster. All victims must be evacuated immediately, without assessing critical versus non-critical conditions. Medical treatment is provided outside the affected area by medical teams.

The use of UGVs must reflect and follow current protocols; their use should not change the way rescue teams operate.

Current usage of technology

Drones – There is a wide spectrum of drones, ranging from simple models that can carry small objects or be used for localization inside buildings where GPS does not work, to more complex and larger drones capable of lifting and transporting victims to medical centres. Land robots – Their use is generally more limited and depends on the type of terrain. They are mainly used to carry tools and deliver them to specific teams when needed. They can also be deployed instead of humans inside buildings or used to patrol areas where it may be unsafe for responders. Main scope of technological tools – These tools are generally used for simple and repetitive tasks that are preferable for robots rather than humans. Robots are often deployed instead of first responders when there is a safety risk for the team and are also used for mapping affected areas.

UGVs are mainly used to gather information. The primary assessment of a victim is carried out by a medical expert, who makes the final decision. There is no need to communicate with headquarters at this stage, and UGVs are not used for direct medical assessment. Drones and robots are used for wide-area assessment.

Robots are important for land detection and fire detection over wide areas through drones. In the past three years, many fires have also been detected by cameras as part of preventive strategies. It is very important to try to prevent large fires.

- When a fire is extinguished, robots can be used to check if there is a possibility of the fire starting again. Many fires are difficult to extinguish completely.
- Robots are also used post-operation to create a disaster map. This is very important for assessing the extent of the damage and is often requested by authorities and politicians.

To sum up, the main tasks where robots can be used are:

- assessment and detection of dangers and victims
- creating a map of the affected area before the operation, from wide areas down to the interior of buildings
- streaming what team members see to the team leader
- post-operation creation of a disaster map

Robots are very important in firefighting. They can bring tools, cameras, gas detection and radiation detection systems, infrared sensors, etc. They can be used to gather a lot of information for the team

leader. Gas detection is especially important, particularly the ability to detect different types of gas (methane, carbon monoxide, etc.) through sensors.

Other studies. Viva Tech: Drones and cars, Fire spread prediction: AI is used to estimate where and how a fire is spreading over an area—for example, what will happen in 20 minutes, whether it will move left or right, etc. This is very helpful for making decisions on how to respond.

Challenges of robot/UGV integration

Technical problems

Robots cannot perform a proper initial assessment of a victim. They can collect some basic parameters (such as temperature or checking whether the victim can speak or breathe), but they cannot measure heart rate or blood pressure, or ensure that the victim has no bleeding. They are also unable to assess whether a victim falls into a green or red triage category.

Ethical and legal problems (AI Act)

Especially in decision-making, robots cannot be autonomous; a human must always be in the loop. For example, a robot should not be used to decide whether a victim is in critical condition or not, nor can it make life-and-death decisions. Currently, robots can be used to provide information, but not to make decisions.

Connectivity as a key issue in UGV use

Fires – These incidents almost always occur in open areas, so connectivity issues are not rare. It is uncommon for both GPS and 4G networks to be unavailable. Earthquakes – Connectivity is not guaranteed. For this reason, it is essential that each first responder team can operate autonomously, without relying on communication with headquarters.

Due to connectivity limitations, the UGV operator should always be in the field with the team leader, rather than at headquarters. This allows the team leader to receive all relevant information locally from the UGV.

If connectivity is available, and if possible, UGV data can also be shared with headquarters, but this is not mandatory. What is mandatory is that UGV information is available locally to the team so they can operate and make decisions based on the collected data.

In firefighting, robots may have problems with **smoke, wind, and rain**, which makes them difficult to use, but they are still possible.

Communication during operations

If internet connectivity is available (for example, during open-air fires), even when the connection is technically good, the network is often saturated by calls. In such cases, communication with headquarters is usually done through messaging applications, as text messages are more likely to get through. Smartphones, however, are not considered standard equipment because internet access cannot always be guaranteed.

If there is no internet connection, teams sometimes set up a local Wi-Fi network with a messaging application. Otherwise, they rely on mobile radios such as VHF and UHF.

In general, teams do not rely heavily on technology to communicate among themselves; they mainly use verbal communication. Technology is primarily needed for communication with headquarters.

The team is made up of many squads. Each squad has a squad leader, for example a USR squad leader, a drone squad leader, or a medical squad leader. The squad leader collects information using robots or other tools and sends the information to the team leader, who is the head of all squads. The team leader puts all the information together to make decisions. Team members mostly communicate verbally because they work very close to each other. When they are far apart, they use WhatsApp, especially for

communication between the team leader and HQ. In this sense, it is important to have a stable connection. They use Starlink, a satellite connection, which is generally very robust.

Interface-related criticalities of desktop application

When interacting with participants with experience in coordinating emergency operations and extensive familiarity with dedicated tools such as web-based coordination platforms, the interviews focused on their perceptions of interface-related challenges associated with this role.

Overall, participants reported that interface criticalities emerge differently depending on the characteristics of the operational scenario. In large-scale emergency operations, involving multiple worksites and several teams operating concurrently, the main difficulty was related to the need to manage a high number of elements simultaneously. Maintaining situational awareness in these contexts was described as highly demanding, as operators must continuously navigate across different sections of the interface to keep track of evolving events.

A major issue concerned the absence of effective notification and alert mechanisms capable of dynamically highlighting relevant information. Requests and updates from field teams or local authorities were often embedded within specific interface sections, requiring operators to proactively check multiple views. This interaction pattern was reported to increase the risk of missing critical information and to slow down coordination and decision-making processes.

One participant described an interface configuration in which information related to different activities was organized into separate tabs. Each tab contained multiple data streams, and notifications were displayed only within the corresponding tab. Consequently, if the operator was not actively viewing that tab, relevant information could remain unnoticed. This was perceived as particularly problematic under time pressure. Interviewees suggested that relatively simple design solutions, such as crosstab pop-up notifications or persistent alerts, could significantly improve information visibility.

Beyond high-tempo, large-scale operations, similar interface limitations were also reported in less complex scenarios characterized by a slower pace of activity. In these situations, the lack of salient notifications and alerts was associated with under-stimulation of attentional resources, potentially leading to reduced vigilance and delayed reactions. Participants highlighted that coordination interfaces should therefore be designed to support both high workload and low workload conditions, mitigating risks related to both information overload and underload.

Additional concerns emerged regarding the uniform treatment of information regardless of its criticality. Participants reported that all notifications were often presented with the same visual prominence, forcing operators to manually assess priorities. This was perceived as cognitively inefficient, particularly in scenarios with concurrent events. Several interviewees suggested that intelligent prioritization mechanisms or recommendation systems could support operators by organizing notifications according to urgency and operational relevance.

Finally, participants emphasized that interface complexity and interaction costs directly affect stress levels and trust in the system. Excessive navigation, frequent context switching, and uncertainty about whether relevant information had been missed were described as contributing factors to cognitive strain. Interviewees therefore highlighted the importance of interface designs that minimize unnecessary interactions, provide reassurance about system status, and support continuous awareness without requiring constant manual checking.

Interface-related criticalities of mobile applications

When interacting with participants with experience as first responders operating in the field, interviews focused on the use of mobile applications designed to support communication with other teams and with the headquarters. Participants described working conditions characterized by dynamic and often chaotic environments, where responders are required to wear bulky protective equipment such as helmets, gloves, and heavy clothing. In this context, their primary attention is devoted to operational

and physical tasks, making interaction with a mobile device a secondary and often non-prioritized activity.

Interviewees consistently reported limited availability of attentional resources for actively monitoring a mobile application. Responders emphasized that they cannot continuously check their phones while performing field operations, as their focus must remain on the surrounding environment, team coordination on-site, and task execution. Consequently, information that requires frequent manual consultation of the application risks being overlooked or accessed with significant delay.

Interaction with mobile devices was described as further constrained by the physical equipment worn by responders. Gloves and protective gear reduce precision when using touchscreens, making small buttons, complex gestures, or multi-step navigation particularly impractical. Environmental conditions such as noise, smoke, low visibility, and adverse weather were also reported to negatively affect the usability of mobile interfaces in the field.

Participants highlighted that checking the mobile application is rarely considered a priority during critical phases of an operation. Interaction with the device typically occurs only during brief pauses or when operational demands temporarily decrease. This interaction pattern increases the risk that important updates, alerts, or requests from other teams or the headquarters may not be noticed in a timely manner.

As a result, interviewees stressed the importance of relying on push-based information delivery rather than on active exploration of the interface. Critical information should be delivered to the responder in a way that does not require continuous attention to the device. Passive monitoring approaches were generally considered unsuitable for field conditions.

The salience and prioritization of notifications emerged as key design concerns. Participants reported that alerts must be sufficiently noticeable to capture attention in noisy and visually demanding environments, while at the same time being carefully filtered to avoid overload. Excessive or poorly prioritized notifications were described as disruptive and potentially dangerous, as they may be ignored altogether, undermining trust in the system.

Timing and relevance of information were also emphasized as critical factors. Information delivered through the mobile application must be closely aligned with the responder's current task, role, and operational context. Updates perceived as irrelevant or arriving too late were considered ineffective and contributed to cognitive burden rather than support.

Finally, interviewees discussed the potential of multimodal interaction strategies to mitigate some of these challenges. Audio and haptic alerts were identified as valuable complements to visual notifications, as they allow responders to receive information without diverting visual attention from the environment. However, participants cautioned that such modalities should be used selectively, as excessive auditory or tactile stimulation could increase stress or confusion in already demanding situations. Overall, trust in mobile applications was described as strongly dependent on their ability to deliver relevant, timely, and actionable information while minimally interfering with the responder's primary operational tasks.

Augmented reality

There are many potential applications for augmented reality, but there are also significant limitations, as the technology is not yet mature. Augmented reality systems can take the form of full-face visors or glasses.

Full-face visors

Pros:

- Support for night vision and thermal vision

- Ability to share what the responder sees in real time with headquarters (for example, to support medical assistance to victims)

Cons:

- Reduced connection with the surrounding environment
- Immature technology with low resolution and connectivity issues, making it unreliable for search and rescue operations
- Heavy equipment that can cause eye strain, headaches, and discomfort
- Potential to distract responders
- Can obstruct operations when they need to be removed to assist a victim; responders already wear helmets, making them difficult to use in practice

Glasses

Pros:

- Lightweight
- Better awareness of the real environment
- Less obstructive during operations

Cons:

- Fewer applications
- Limited mainly to displaying indicators such as text or 3D maps

The main purpose of augmented reality is to merge and aggregate information from different tools in order to present relevant data, such as the location of victims and the positions of team members.

Currently, most commercial models are designed for static environments, especially full-face visors, and are not suited for dynamic emergency situations such as fires or disasters. At present, augmented reality is more useful for headquarters than for first responders in the field. Ideally, once the technology matures, augmented reality should be deployed from headquarters down to team leaders and team members. Equipping team leaders with AR glasses would be highly beneficial, as they could use them to guide their teams more effectively.

Many tele pilots work with drones, and the team leader uses Google Glasses, for instance, to see what is happening inside a building. This is very helpful for danger detection. Augmented reality is important for danger and victim detection. The ability to stream what a team member sees through Google Glasses to the team leader is very important.

4.3 Insights on specific human-robot interaction situations

A specific focus during the interviews was on the usage of robotic platforms to support victim identification and support. The following main aspects emerged.

Victim detection and area mapping

- Victim detection was described as a phased process:
 - Mapping a wide area to identify potential victim locations.
 - Narrowing focus to specific areas with a higher concentration of victims.
- A combination of assets is typically used:
 - Aerial drones are primarily suited for large-area mapping.
 - Dogs are considered more effective for locating victims inside buildings.
 - UGVs are preferred over humans for entering unsafe or unstable environments

- UGVs were described as complementary tools rather than replacements for human responders or animals.

Triage protocol for multiple victims

- When multiple victims are detected, responders apply a triage protocol to prioritize intervention.
- Victims are categorized based on severity:
 - Green: less critical.
 - Red: most critical.
- Triage is a classification task performed under time and resource constraints.
- Interviewees emphasized that:
 - UGVs may support data collection relevant to triage.
 - UGVs must not autonomously decide victim priority or criticality.
 - A human decision-maker must remain responsible for triage classification.

First victim assessment (Primary assessment)

- For each victim, responders aim to determine whether the person could die within the next three minutes.
- This assessment follows standard protocols such as:
 - Basic Life Support (BLS).
 - European Resuscitation Council (ERC) guidelines.
- Key checks include:
 - Presence of severe bleeding.
 - Breathing.
 - Heartbeat.
- **UGVs were described as capable of supporting this phase indirectly through sensing and communication, but not of executing medical decisions.**

First assessment when the victim is not visible or is trapped

- When a victim cannot be visually assessed (e.g. trapped under debris), interviewees reported that only limited checks are possible via UGV interaction.
- A psychological assessment cannot be reliably performed using voice alone.
- Two elements were identified as assessable through vocal interaction:
 - Responsiveness
 - The UGV may ask basic questions (e.g. name, location awareness).
 - A response indicates that the victim is breathing and that cardiac activity is present.
 - Lack of response suggests a more critical situation.
 - Emotional state
 - Responders assess whether the victim appears calm or panicked.
 - A panicked emotional state may indicate higher risk or worsening conditions.
- These checks were described as proxies rather than full assessments.

Limitations of victim self-assessment

- Interviewees noted that victims can verbally report their condition, but:
 - Self-assessment is not considered reliable.
 - Adrenaline may prevent both victims and responders from noticing bleeding or pain.
 - Internal bleeding or non-visible injuries are often undetected by the victim.

- As a result, UGV-facilitated self-reporting was viewed as informative but insufficient for clinical decision-making.

Secondary assessment

- Once a victim passes the primary assessment, a secondary assessment is conducted.
- This phase aims to determine whether the victim's condition could worsen in the coming hours.
- Responders check for:
 - Fractures.
 - Allergies.
 - Medications.
 - Relevant medical history.
- Secondary assessment focuses on understanding the mechanism of injury and stabilizing the victim.
- This task is typically performed by trained paramedics and is considered a core part of their professional training. UGVs could be partially supported by acting as remote sensing instruments for paramedics.

Victim assistance and support

- Beyond assessment, UGVs were described as able to assist victims by:
 - Providing verbal reassurance.
 - Calming panicked victims through voice interaction.
 - Monitoring conditions while awaiting responders.
 - Escorting victims to safer areas when feasible.
 - Delivering basic support items (e.g. first aid kit, water, gas mask).
- A typical example cited was defibrillator delivery:
 - A drone may deliver the device.
 - A human must operate it.
 - Proper use depends on victim-specific factors (e.g. adult vs. child).

Role of AI and future use of LLMs in secondary assessment

- Interviewees highlighted that identifying internal bleeding or non-visible injuries is particularly challenging.
- AI was discussed as a potential future support tool during the secondary assessment phase:
 - Models trained on a wide range of clinical scenarios could suggest tests or checks.
 - AI outputs would support, not replace, paramedic decision-making.
- Studies on the use of large language models (LLMs) were mentioned as promising for:
 - Scenario interpretation.
 - Decision support.
- Final responsibility for clinical decisions must remain with human medical professionals.

Human-in-the-loop and ethical constraints

- Across all phases, interviewees stressed the importance of a human-in-the-loop approach.
- UGVs should:
 - Operate autonomously at a functional level.
 - Collect and transmit relevant data.
- UGVs should not:

- Be used directly by medical experts as decision-making tools.
- Autonomously classify victim criticality.
- Make medical or ethical judgments.
- Ethical considerations include:
 - Avoiding false reassurance.
 - Preventing over-reliance on automation.
 - Preserving responsibility and accountability with human responders.

Given ethical consideration and that the technology is not mature enough to allow autonomous decision-making, Table 3 shows an overview of possible tasks that can be done with the remote support of an expert, in the attempt to speed up the process while waiting for human intervention and support the EMT work.

Table 3 Tasks that can possibly be done exploiting UGVs in victim rescue activity

Emergency Phase	Protocol / Task	UGV Functional Requirement	Sensors /Actuators Outputs	Constraints / Notes
Area mapping	Victim detection (wide area)	Map large areas to identify potential victim locations	Camera, LiDAR, GPS / Locomotion, data transmission	Often complemented by aerial drones; UGVs preferred in unsafe ground environments
Area focusing	Victim localization (dense areas)	Navigate and refine victim location in hazardous zones	Camera, LiDAR, microphone / Locomotion	Dogs considered more effective inside buildings; UGVs used to reduce human risk
Environmental safety	Hazard detection	Detect gas leaks and chemical hazards	Chemical sensors / Communication module, locomotion	Sensor readings must be contextually interpreted
Environmental safety	Electrical hazard inference	Identify indirect indicators of electricity	Camera / Locomotion	Cannot detect electricity directly

Triage	Multi-victim prioritization	Collect and transmit victim-related data relevant for triage	Camera, microphone, thermal sensor / Communication module	UGV must not autonomously classify victims (green/red); human remains responsible
Primary assessment	First victim assessment (BLS / ERC)	Support evaluation of immediate life risk (\leq 3 minutes)	Camera, microphone, thermal sensor / Speaker, communication module	No autonomous medical decisions; data supports human judgment
Primary assessment	Severe bleeding check	Detect visible bleeding	Camera / None	Limited to visible cues; internal bleeding not detectable
Primary assessment	Breathing and heartbeat inference	Infer breathing/heartbeat via responsiveness and movement	Camera, microphone / Speaker	Chest movement detection unreliable with current data
Primary assessment (Trapped victim)	Responsiveness check	Ask basic questions (name, orientation)	Microphone / Speaker	Response implies breathing and cardiac activity
Primary assessment (Trapped victim)	Emotional state estimation	Identify panic vs. calm state	Microphone / Speaker	Psychological assessment cannot rely on voice alone
Secondary assessment	Injury and risk evaluation	Support data collection for fractures, pain, medical history	Camera, microphone / Speaker, communication module	Conducted by paramedics; UGV supports but does not assess clinically

Secondary assessment	Medical history collection	Ask about allergies, medications, prior conditions	Microphone / Speaker	Victim self-reporting might be unreliable due to adrenaline or hidden injuries
Victim support	Psychological support	Calm and reassure the victim	Microphone / Speaker	Avoid false reassurance; tone must be controlled
Victim support	Pain monitoring	Ask about pain and discomfort	Microphone / Speaker	Informative only; not diagnostic
Victim support	Escort to safety	Guide victim to safer location when feasible	Camera, LiDAR / Locomotion	Only if victim is mobile and environment is safe
Victim support	Resource delivery	Deliver first aid kit, water, gas mask, AED	Camera, proximity sensors / Manipulator or payload system	Devices (e.g. AED) must be used by humans
Handover	Information transfer	Report victim and environment status to responders	All relevant sensors / Communication module	Supports smooth transition to human care
Ethical oversight	Human-in-the-loop	Ensure control decisions human over	System-level monitoring / Override reporting mechanisms	UGV autonomy limited to operational tasks

5 Recommendations for design and evaluation

Some recommendations emerged from the efforts carried out in the work previously described. More in detail, Table 4 synthesises the most significant outcomes at system level, at HRI level, at HCI level and AR level.

Table 4 Recommendations for system design and development to preserve human factors

ID	Recommendations	Human factor implication	Related URs
SYSTEM			
HF_01_01	The use of technology must reflect and follow current protocols; their use should not disrupt the way rescue teams operate.	To be effectively well received, and increase trust, should be integrated in a seamless manner. This will give the responders the time to familiarize and rely on “unconventional” support.	U1_01
HF_01_02	Ethical and legal problems	Especially in decision-making that implies taking decisions on human beings' safety, technology cannot be autonomous. Human-mediated decisions are mandatory	U1.08.b, U1.12.e
HF_01_03	Connectivity aspects	Connectivity issues are crucial to foster communication. Failures might affect humans' trust in technology, as well as undermine SA levels and teamwork due to lack of communication.	U1_04, U1.06, U1.11, U1.13
HF_01_04	Communication between human in the field and non-human agents to be preferred via short-range infrastructure	Ensuring back-up communication channels between UGV/UAV and FRs in the field could mitigate the risk of distress in FRs in case connectivity issues occur in long-range communication (FRs-headquarter, UAV/UGV-headquarter). Data from UGV/UAV directly sent to FRs in the field.	U1.13
HF_01_05	AI supports the prediction of wind direction during fires. Estimation of fire spreading.	Helpful in supporting decision making and managing time pressure. Possibly reducing stress, modulating workload, and increasing SA.	U1.02.d
HF_01_06	System behaviour should be predictable and consistent across scenarios.	Supports trust formation and reduces mental workload.	U1.02.d

HF_01_07	Dedicated technology-oriented training for FRs	Training to new technologies is crucial to ensure effective and confident use during real emergencies. It can increase trust towards technology and better awareness on possible advantages.	U1_01
HF_01_08	Tailored training curricula	Personalizing training programs according to individual characteristics can help FRs in gradually become self-confident in their capabilities, increasing trust, self-efficacy and supporting incremental resilience capabilities while avoiding oversteering	U1_01
HRI			
HF_02_01	UAVs and UGVs used for simple and repetitive tasks	This can relieve humans from tasks that require sustained attention for prolonged time and possibly physical workload.	U1.10
HF_02_02	UAVs and UGVs used for wide-area assessment. Preventive usage UAVs – monitoring, land and fire detection	Before the emergency, usage of technology can prevent the occurrence of an emergency situation and can allow tempestive intervention reducing the risks for responders and preserving their mental wellbeing.	U1.03.a, U1.06, U1.07, U1.10, U1.11
HF_02_03	UAVs and UGVs used for wide-area assessment. Emergency phase – detection of danger and victims, map of the affected area to guide the operations (both wide area and interior of buildings)	During the emergency occurrence, the usage of UAVs and UGVs can support the first responders in enhancing their SA by supporting the detection of situations and facilitating the identification of working sites.	U1.03.a, U1.06, U1.07, U1.08.b, U1.10, U1.11
HF_02_04	UAVs and UGVs used for wide-area assessment. Post emergency – patrolling and disaster map.	While performing patrolling tasks on behalf of humans, robots preserve them from stressful and boring tasks. At the same time, SA can be increased.	U1.03.c, U1.06, U1.10, U1.11
HF_02_05	UAVs and UGVs – streamed information to team leaders	While streaming contextual information in real-time, FRs can build up an overview of the situation in a timely manner. This might help increase their SA and modulate stress levels.	U1.03.a, U1.07, U1.08.b, U1.10
HF_02_06	UGVs (and UAVs) as support for physical tasks like bringing tools	According to the payload characteristics of the robotic platform, by taking over such tasks, UGVs could relieve FRs from physical workload and possibly focus on more crucial activities.	U1.10

HF_02_07	UGVs and UAVs (equipped with sensors) as support for detection of dangerous situations, like gas leaking or radiation presence.	In this case, by supporting this type of tasks, the FRs' sense of safety can be preserved, without affecting their level of SA.	U1.03.a, U1.05, U1.10
HF_02_09	Proximity aspects for UGV/UAV modulated according to the users approaching	Proximity to human beings should be modulated according to the familiarity of the person approaching. Familiarity with the platform should be taken into consideration in order not to increase stress levels. More attention should be paid in case of approaching victims (e.g. slower pace, possibly not within personal distance)	U1.02.d, U1.08, U1.10
HCI			
C2 PLATFORM			
HF_03_01	Interfaces should reduce unnecessary interaction steps and context switching.	Lowers cognitive strain and stress, especially during prolonged operations.	U1.02.b, U1.06.f, U1.09
HF_03_02	Interface should minimize the need for continuous manual navigation across views.	Reduces cognitive load, context switching, and the risk of missing critical information, supporting sustained SA.	U1.02.b, U1.06.d, U1.06.f, U1.09
HF_03_03	Critical information should be visible regardless of the currently active interface view.	Prevents attentional tunneling and information loss under time pressure.	U1.02.b, U1.09
HF_03_04	Notification mechanisms should operate across interface sections (e.g. crosstab alerts).	Supports rapid detection of relevant events without requiring proactive checking. It allows an increase of SA, reduces workload and stress levels.	U1.02.b, U1.03.a, U1.09
HF_03_05	Notifications and alerts should be differentiated by urgency and criticality.	Supports attentional prioritization and reduces cognitive effort in emergency decision-making.	U1.02.b, U1.03.a, U1.09
HF_03_06	The system should provide feedback indicating whether critical information has been acknowledged or not.	Reduces uncertainty, stress, and distrust related to potential missed information.	U1.09

HF_03_07	Persistent alerts should be used for high-criticality events until acknowledged.	Prevents loss of critical information during multitasking and high workload conditions.	U1.03.a, U1.09
HF_03_08	Multimodal alerting (visual and auditory) should be considered for high-priority events.	Enhances detection under high workload or visual saturation, supporting attentional resource allocation.	U1.02.a, U1.03.a, U1.09
HF_03_09	Interfaces should support both high-tempo and low-tempo operational conditions.	Mitigates risks associated with both information overload and underload, preserving vigilance and performance.	U1.02.d, U1.06.d, U1.09
HF_03_10	Recommendation systems should support prioritization of events and notifications.	Reduces cognitive burden and supports timely decision-making without replacing human judgment.	U1.02.d, U1.03.a, U1.09
HF_03_11	AI-based prioritization should be transparent and adjustable by the operator.	Prevents automation bias and supports trust calibration.	U1.02.b, U1.02.d, U1.03.a, U1.08.b, U1.09
HF_03_12	Decision-support tools should highlight why an event is considered critical.	Enhances interpretability and supports informed human decisions under stress.	U1.02.d, U1.03.a, U1.09
HF_03_13	Interface designs should provide reassurance that the system is actively monitoring events.	Reduces anxiety related to potential information loss and improves perceived reliability.	U1.02.d, U1.03.a, U1.09
MOBILE APP			
HF_04_01	Mobile applications for first responders should rely primarily on push-based information delivery rather than requiring active consultation	Reduces attentional demands and the need for proactive monitoring, supporting situation awareness in highly dynamic and physically demanding contexts	U1.02.b, U1.03.a
HF_04_02	Critical information should be surfaced independently of the current screen or interaction state	Prevents loss of information due to navigation constraints and mitigates attentional tunnelling	U1.02.d, U1.03.a
HF_04_03	Interfaces should be usable with minimal visual attention	Supports multitasking in chaotic environments and reduces interference with primary operational tasks	U1.02.a, U1.02.b
HF_04_04	Interaction should be optimized for use with gloves and protective equipment	Reduces physical and cognitive workload, frustration, and interaction errors	U1.02.a

HF_04_05	The number of interaction steps required to access critical functions should be minimized	Limits context switching and preserves attentional resources under time pressure	U1.02.b, U1.06.f
HF_04_06	Notifications should be prioritized based on urgency and operational relevance	Prevents information overload and supports effective allocation of attentional resources	U1.02.d, U1.03.a
HF_04_07	High-criticality alerts should be persistent until acknowledged	Reduces the risk of missed information and increases trust in the system	U1.03.a
HF_04_08	Non-critical notifications should be suppressible or grouped	Mitigates alert fatigue and avoids unnecessary distractions	U1.03.a
HF_04_09	Multimodal alerts (visual, auditory, haptic) should be selectively employed	Enables information uptake without requiring constant visual attention	U1.02.a, U1.03.a, U1.09.b
HF_04_10	Auditory alerts should be carefully calibrated to avoid stress or confusion	Balances vigilance support with emotional and cognitive load	U1.02.a, U1.03.a
HF_04_11	The system should support both high-tempo and low-tempo operational phases	Prevents cognitive overload during peak activity and under-stimulation during quieter periods	U1.02.d
HF_04_12	Adaptive notification strategies should be considered based on operational tempo	Supports sustained vigilance and reduces attentional degradation over time	U1.02.d
HF_04_13	Interfaces should emphasize actionable information only	Preserves SA by avoiding unnecessary cognitive processing	U1.02.d
HF_04_14	Information delivered to first responders should be filtered based on role, task, and location	Reduces irrelevant information and supports local SA, modulate workload and stress level	U1.02.d, U1.03.d, U1.03.a, U1.09.b
HF_04_15	The system should avoid delivering information that cannot be acted upon immediately	Prevents frustration and cognitive overload	U1.02.d
HF_04_16	Context-aware filtering should be transparent to the user	Enhances trust and predictability of system behaviour	U1.02.d, U1.09.b

HF_04_17	The system should provide feedback indicating that critical events are being monitored	Reduces uncertainty and perceived need for constant checking	
HF_04_18	Technology should support, not replace, human decision-making	Preserves sense of control and aligns with ethical and legal constraints	U1.03.a
AUGMENTED REALITY			
HF_05_01	Augmented reality used by FRs in the field Full-face visors - pros	Offers the possibility to share what the FRs who wear it with others increase communication, teamwork, remote support	U1.12.d
HF_05_02	Augmented reality used by FRs in the field Full-face visors - cons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discomfortable, especially if put with other equipment (e.g. helmet) • Can negatively affect SA (isolation from the physical environment) • Subjected by connectivity issues that can negatively influence user's workload 	U1.12.d
HF_05_03	Augmented reality Glasses – pros	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More ergonomic • Can allow better SA integrating info from physical environment to virtual info (e.g. receiving notifications) 	U1.12.d
HF_05_04	Integration AR with UAV/UGV	Streaming information gathered by UAVs and UGVs to the AR device worn by first responders can enhance their SA by complementing their direct perception of the surrounding environment with remotely acquired information.	U1.02.a
HF_05_05	Integration AR with HCI interface C2 platform	Complementing the information visualized through the C2 platform with that provided via AR can enhance situational awareness while distributing workload and attentional resources. For example, the C2 platform can focus on ongoing events, whereas AR can present temporary information such as notifications or high-priority alerts	U1.02.a

With respect to the evaluation aspects, specifically focused on human factors, it will be surely useful to consider the investigation of Usability aspects. Some examples of self-report instruments can be the System Usability Scale (SUS; [Brooke96]), a simple, ten-item Likert scale giving a global view of subjective assessments of usability. This instrument can be used for assessing the usability of the overall TRIFFID system. An instrument more focused on HCI that can be used is the Computer System Usability Questionnaire (CSUQ; Lewis, 1996). It is a standardized questionnaire developed by the Human-Computer Interaction Lab at the University of Maryland to measure user satisfaction with computer systems. It contains 19 items rated on a 7-point Likert scale, assessing system quality, information, interface, and overall satisfaction. The think aloud [Ericsson93] technique represents another qualitative methodology to investigate usability. It requires the participants to verbalize thoughts while performing a task and it is useful during intermediate assessments to gather feedback aimed at feeding development refinements.

An instrument specifically focused on the HRI aspects can be the Self-Efficacy in Human-Robot Interaction Scale (SE-HRI; [Rosenthal18]), a psychometric scale developed to measure an individual's perceived self-efficacy when interacting with robots — that is, the belief in one's ability to successfully perform actions and handle tasks involving robots. It assesses people's judgments of what they can do with robots (e.g., operating, controlling, learning to use them), using items rated on a Likert scale.

Another aspect worthy to be investigated while assessing the usage of a technological platform as support in operation is represented by trust toward technology. Some instruments applicable to the interaction with autonomous or semi-autonomous platforms are the Trust in Automation Questionnaire [Chen11] and the Trust in Automation Scale [Jian00].

Beside, the just mentioned instruments, the ones mentioned in section 2.1 can be surely taken into consideration.

For what concerns the possibility to exploit qualitative methodology, it has already just mentioned the possibility to apply the EAST framework. In fact, the EAST framework supports both the design and development of sociotechnical systems for emergency management and the evaluation of the resulting system, with a specific focus on human factors. In the evaluation phase, the framework can be applied to assess how the deployed system performs within the broader sociotechnical context and how it affects human factors outcomes.

In this context, Hierarchical Task Analysis can be used to compare expected versus actual task execution, identifying changes in task distribution, workload, or coordination introduced by the system. This supports the evaluation of whether the technology effectively simplifies work processes or inadvertently introduces new complexities. Cognitive Decision Method enables the assessment of how the system influences decision-making, trust, and reliance on technology, particularly in critical situations. By examining decision points before and after system introduction, evaluators can determine whether the system supports timely and informed decisions, or whether it leads to over-reliance, misinterpretation, or reduced vigilance. EAST provides a system-level evaluation by analysing changes in task, social, and information networks. This allows the identification of mismatches or breakdowns in information flow, reductions or increases in coordination demands, and the extent to which distributed situation awareness is maintained or degraded. Importantly, EAST supports the identification of emergent effects that are not visible when focusing on individual users alone. Together, the framework enables a comprehensive evaluation of the system's impact on stress, workload, situation awareness, trust, and overall system resilience, providing evidence-based guidance for system refinement and future iterations. In appendix 2, a participatory design toolkit is provided with possible

methodologies and instruments to investigate human factors by involving the end users throughout the design and development path

6 Conclusions

This deliverable presented a comprehensive human factors analysis and participatory design framework developed within the TRIFFID project, with the aim of supporting the design, development, and evaluation of human–robot teaming technologies for disaster response and emergency management. By integrating insights from the literature, empirical investigations, and qualitative participatory activities, the document provided a structured understanding of how individual, contextual, and socio-technical factors influence first responders’ performance, wellbeing, and interaction with advanced technological systems.

At the individual level, the analysis highlighted the role of stable personal characteristics, such as personality traits, coping strategies, decision-making styles, and self-efficacy, in shaping how first responders perceive and manage stress, workload, and situation awareness in high-pressure environments. The findings suggest that adaptive coping strategies, cognitive flexibility, and high perceived self-efficacy function as protective factors that support effective cognitive processing and situational understanding, whereas maladaptive coping patterns and excessive reflexivity may negatively affect cognitive clarity and perceived resource availability. These insights underline the importance of considering individual differences when designing training pathways and support mechanisms aimed at enhancing resilience and operational effectiveness.

At the socio-technical level, the deliverable adopted a systems perspective grounded in Distributed Situation Awareness and operationalised through the Event Analysis of Systemic Teamwork (EAST) framework. By combining Hierarchical Task Analysis and the Critical Decision Method, the analysis captured how tasks, decisions, information flows, and social interactions are distributed across human and non-human agents in emergency response operations. This approach enabled the identification of coordination demands, information dependencies, and potential vulnerabilities emerging from the interaction between responders, robotic platforms, and command-and-control systems. Importantly, it demonstrated the value of analysing human–robot interaction not in isolation, but as part of a broader socio-technical system.

The participatory design methodologies described in this deliverable, including contextual inquiry, interviews, workshops, personas, and scenario-based design, ensured that end-user perspectives were systematically incorporated throughout the analysis. Grounding design considerations in real operational practices and constraints proved essential for identifying user needs, ethical concerns, and trust-related issues that may not be evident through purely technical analyses. This participatory approach supports the development of human-centred solutions that align with existing protocols, roles, and decision-making structures in emergency management.

Based on the integrated human factors analysis, the deliverable formulated a set of design and evaluation recommendations for the TRIFFID system. These recommendations address system-level integration, human–robot interaction, human–computer interaction, and augmented reality components, with particular attention to usability, workload management, situation awareness, trust, and ethical and legal constraints. Collectively, they emphasise that technology should support and augment human decision-making rather than replace it, and that reliability, transparency, and predictability are key prerequisites for user acceptance in safety-critical contexts.

Overall, this deliverable contributes a methodological and conceptual foundation for embedding human factors and participatory design principles into the TRIFFID project. The insights and recommendations

provided are intended to guide subsequent development, integration, and evaluation activities, supporting the creation of robust, usable, and ethically sound human–robot teaming solutions that enhance first responders’ effectiveness while safeguarding their wellbeing. Future work will build on these findings through iterative system refinement and empirical evaluation in realistic operational settings.

This deliverable can contribute to the evolving EU first responders doctrine by providing evidence-based guidelines on how human factors, sociotechnical integration, and participatory design can enhance operational effectiveness and resilience in emergency response. By addressing human factors in human–robot and human–AI collaboration, the proposed recommendations support faster, safer, and more coordinated response operations in line with the objectives of the Union Civil Protection Mechanism. The emphasis on distributed situation awareness contributes to preparedness and risk management by supporting the development and validation of common operational procedures and training practices for complex, multi-actor emergency contexts. Overall, the deliverable offers transferable methodological and design principles that can support the consolidation of a more human-centred, and resilient approach to disaster response.

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Appendix 1 - Interviews' guide

The following guide was used to perform both interviews and workshops by applying the HTA and CDM. According to the different situations it was slightly adapted to fit with the contextual needs (e.g. individual interviews, field inquiries, workshop).

Table 5 Interview protocol for goal analysis and decision-making in emergency scenarios

	Probes:
Thinking about a ... emergency scenario can you describe which are the main goals to reach in order to face the emergency?	<p>Think about high level goals, these might be related to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information processing • environment monitoring, • civilians monitoring, • damage assessments, • etc. <p>Do you see any priorities among goals? Are there some goals to achieve in parallel?</p>
For each goal just identified, I would like to reason together about the task(s) to achieve it. Let's start with (proceed according to priorities)	<p>For each task, investigate:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who carries the task out • How often are tasks carried out? • Which decisions must be taken • What information is needed for taking decisions? • What are the consequences of actions and what feedback is provided? • What is the temporal relation of tasks? • What are the consequences of actions and what feedback is provided?
Let's discuss a specific situation you were in, and you felt it was difficult to manage ... goal specification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What were your specific goals at the various decision points?
Cue Identification	<p>What features were you looking for when you formulated your decision? How did you know that you needed to make the decision? How did you know when to make a decision?</p>
Expectancy Were you expecting to make this sort of decision during the course of the event?	Describe how this affected your decision-making process
Conceptual Are there any situations in which your decision would have turned out differently?	Describe the nature of these situations and the characteristics that would have changed the outcome of your decisions

<p>Influence of uncertainty</p>	<p>At any stage, were you uncertain about the reliability of the relevance of the information that you had available? At any stage, were you uncertain about the appropriateness of the decision?</p>
<p>Information integration</p>	<p>What was the most important piece of information that you used to formulate the decision?</p>
<p>Situation awareness and assessment What information did you have available to you at the time of the decision?</p>	<p>Did you use all of them? Was there any additional info that you might have used to assist in the formulation of the decision? Do you see any possibility that technology could support you? AI, robotics, etc.</p>
<p>Decision blocking – stress Was there any stage during the decision-making process in which you found it difficult to process and integrate the information available?</p>	<p>Try to describe precisely the nature of the situation Was it because of your uncertainty? Was it because of missing information or the shape of information? Do you think that technological support could be helpful? If yes, how? If not, why?</p>

Appendix 2 - Participatory design toolkit

The following figure represents the most important phases of a participatory design approach during which the involvement of stakeholders becomes crucial.

Understanding users’ needs: This phase focuses on gathering the user requirements by taking into account human factors. The goal here is to gather feedback to guide the design and the development of the system.

Formative assessment: these activities support the assessment and evaluation of the different modules of the system in a controlled environment. The goal here is to ensure the development of robust and reliable technology, allowing the necessary technical refinement before the integration and the deployment of the system in an ecological setting.

Ecological assessment: The whole system is evaluated in its final application in the field. The goal of the assessment in this phase is to mostly investigate the impact of the usage in realistic scenarios.

Figure 9 Iterative human-centred design and validation process

For each phase, specific methodologies and instruments are suggested according to the objectives of that phase, in order to support the proper design and development of the TRIFFID system. The instruments are described in detail in the deliverable; here, they are reported according to the phase in which they can be most appropriately applied.

Table 6 Methodologies and instruments across user needs elicitation, formative and ecological assessment

Methodology/Instrument	User needs elicitation	Formative assessment	Ecological assessment
GENERAL PURPOSE			
Design thinking	X		
Interviews	X		X
Workshops	X		
Scenario walkthrough	X		
HUMAN FACTORS			
Situation Awareness			
EAST methodology	X		X
SART-10		X	X
SAGAT			X

Usability			
CSUQ		X	
SUS		X	X
Think aloud		X	
Self-efficacy			
SE-HRI		X	X
Self-efficacy in Crisis			X
Trust			
TAQ		X	X
TAS		X	X
Stress			
SSSQ			X
PSS			X
Workload			
NASA-TLX		X	X
MRS			X
Technology Acceptance			
TAM			X